

Improving Production Efficiency Using Smart Manufacturing Technologies in Manufacturing Industries: A Survey Study at The Northern General Cement Company

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ARTICLE INFO

Online Publication:
27 August 2025

ABSTRACT

The research sought to measure the nature of the correlations and influence between one of the most important modern variables in the industrial field, which plays a pivotal and fundamental role in improving the utilization of various resources in the industrial sector. This variable, namely smart manufacturing, and production efficiency, is a variable that suffers from the failure to achieve optimal levels of utilization of various resources, particularly natural resources, which represent an important source for these industries, particularly in the field of manufacturing industries such as the cement industry. One industrial company (the Northern General Cement Company) was selected to test the research hypotheses to identify the most prominent obstacles facing improving production efficiency and overcoming them through smart manufacturing technologies. The research relied on a hypothetical model that reflects the main research variables. Data was collected from the field under study using a questionnaire, where the questionnaire was distributed equally to the three factories affiliated with the Northern General Cement Company. The research data was analyzed and the research results interpreted. The research reached a set of conclusions, most notably the disparity in the impact of smart manufacturing technologies among the company's factories studied, in addition to the limited level of adoption of these technologies by the studied factories. One of the research's most prominent recommendations is the need for the company's management to adopt smart manufacturing on a broad scale, by integrating its technologies into all areas and stages of cement manufacturing. This is due to its advantages in improving production efficiency, including increased productivity, reduced waste of natural resources, and maximized utilization. It also promotes environmental conservation and sustainability, two hallmarks of the modern era.

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KEYWORDS: Production efficiency, smart manufacturing.

INTRODUCTION

Smart manufacturing plays a significant role in all fields, especially in the industrial sector. The importance of modern manufacturing in the industrial sector is evident in its ability to increase and improve product efficiency and productivity. Therefore, countries seek to develop strategies and development plans that promote the use of modern manufacturing and provide the expertise, information, and funding necessary to facilitate the use of this type of manufacturing. They also need to develop infrastructure, provide renewable energy, and provide trained personnel and modern equipment to facilitate the use of modern technology. Over the past few years, manufacturing technology has witnessed tremendous development, leading to the irrational use of resources and energy, negatively impacting production efficiency due to misuse. This, coupled with a growing lack

of awareness among workers, has become an urgent factor driving industrial management to seriously consider these challenges by adopting modern methods and systems that maintain production efficiency, reduce excessive use of resources and energy, and achieve customer satisfaction. Numerous studies and research have confirmed that smart manufacturing processes play a significant and pivotal role in the success of industrial enterprises and maintaining their competitive position. This research is divided into four sections. The first section presents the research methodology, while the second section is devoted to the theoretical aspect of improving production efficiency and smart manufacturing. The third section is devoted to the field aspect, including an analysis of data obtained from the institution under study. The research concludes with a fourth section containing conclusions and recommendations.

Chapter One: Research Methodology

This chapter defines the research problem, its importance, and objectives, constructs its theoretical framework, formulates its hypotheses, and explains the statistical methods used to collect and analyze data, as follows:

First: The Research Problem

Smart manufacturing is one of the newest concepts in industrial and service organizations. Modern technologies have become one of the most important prerequisites of widespread importance for the success of any organization. To enable organizations to gain a sustainable competitive advantage, production processes must be redesigned in more innovative ways that incorporate modern technologies. Therefore, the current research focuses on how to achieve high production efficiency using smart manufacturing. The research problem is that despite the development and emergence of modern technology in the industrial sector, which significantly contributes to increasing industrial sector productivity and the growing trend toward industrial development, the implementation of smart manufacturing still faces many challenges. These challenges include a lack of awareness of the importance of modern smart manufacturing, a shortage of capital, and deteriorating infrastructure, which impact industrial productivity. Furthermore, the workforce's lack of experience in modern manufacturing processes is a major factor, leading to the failure to achieve high production efficiency. Therefore, it is clear that the field under study lacks the ability to achieve production efficiency due to the failure to implement smart manufacturing requirements. Based on the above, the research problem and its causes revolve around determining the role of smart manufacturing and its technologies in improving production efficiency upon application. The research problem can be defined through the following questions:

1. To what extent is smart manufacturing available in the field under study?
2. How efficient is production in the field under study?
3. Is smart manufacturing related to production efficiency in the field under study?
4. Does smart manufacturing affect production efficiency in the field under study?

Second: The Importance of the Research

The research represents a significant addition to knowledge, as its dimensions and implications point to the importance and role of smart manufacturing in improving and raising production efficiency in many manufacturing industries. The importance of the research is evident in the problem it discusses. Undoubtedly, the topics of smart manufacturing and production efficiency have received widespread attention from studies and research, both globally and locally, given the impact of these aspects on public life. Regarding the research area, the importance of the research lies in its attempt

to provide the correct scientific foundations that enable the field studied to understand smart manufacturing and its role in improving production efficiency. The importance of the research is evident in:

1. The importance of the research stems from the importance of integration between smart manufacturing and production efficiency in the field studied.
2. The research also gains its importance from the field studied's orientation toward applying modern methods in the field of operations management, which contributes to achieving environmental protection and enabling survival and growth in the market.
3. The vital importance of the research variables as contemporary approaches that align with the business requirements of contemporary organizations, in addition to the research field's potential to keep pace with the ongoing changes in the field of modern approaches to production operations.

Third: Research Objectives

The research seeks to achieve the following objectives:

1. Present a theoretical and field study in the field of research on smart manufacturing and production efficiency.
2. Determine the level of interest and commitment to smart manufacturing processes and production efficiency in the research area.
3. Examine the relationship between smart manufacturing and production efficiency.
4. Provide some practical treatments and solutions based on the findings of the field results, which provide a clear vision for the integration of smart manufacturing and production efficiency within the research area's environment, thus protecting the natural environment from the negative effects of industrial waste. This is achieved by presenting a number of conclusions based on fundamental foundations to clarify the proposals we deem appropriate for the research area.

Fourth: The hypothetical research plan

After defining the research problem, its importance, and its objectives, a hypothetical model must be designed to address the research problem. This hypothetical model includes smart manufacturing as the (independent variable) and production efficiency as the (dependent variable). Figure (1) illustrates the relationship between the research variables.

Figure (1) Hypothetical research plan

Source: Prepared by researchers

Fifth: Research Hypotheses

In line with the hypothetical plan, the following hypotheses were formulated:

First Main Hypothesis: There is no statistically significant correlation between smart manufacturing and production efficiency in the field under study.

Sub-Hypothesis: There is no statistically significant correlation between any dimension of smart manufacturing and production efficiency in the field under study.

Second Main Hypothesis: There is no statistically significant effect of smart manufacturing on production efficiency in the field under study.

Sub-Hypothesis: There is no statistically significant effect of smart manufacturing on production efficiency in the field under study.

Sixth: Research Methodology

To achieve the study objectives, the descriptive analytical approach was adopted, relying on describing the phenomenon and collecting data and information about the research variables directly from the sample. The type and validity of the data were studied and verified. This approach follows organized steps to identify the tangible and known aspects that play a role in increasing and improving production efficiency.

Seventh: Research Community and Sample: The research community was represented by the company. Northern Cement Company, where a questionnaire was distributed to collect information (34) in each of the company's factories (Sinjar Cement Factory, Badoush Cement Factory, and Hammam Al-Alil Cement Factory) to a sample of employees from various specialties (technicians, engineers, and administrators). Data for each of the company's factories was analyzed separately.

Eighth: Statistical Methods Used in the Research

The researchers relied on a number of statistical methods related to the research variables in an analysis consistent with

their nature. In order to achieve the desired results of the current research, the following methods were adopted:

1- Pearson's Correlation Coefficient to measure the degree of correlation between the research variables.

2- A linear stepwise regression analysis model to measure the degree of influence between the independent variable on the dependent variable.

Section Two: The Theoretical Aspect

Smart Manufacturing

First: The Concept of Smart Manufacturing

Smart Manufacturing (IM) is a true industrial revolution, also known as the Fourth Industrial Revolution. The first was the steam revolution, which emerged in the second half of the eighteenth century and relied on water and steam in production machines. The second was the electricity revolution, which emerged in the nineteenth century and relied on harnessing electrical energy for larger-scale production. The third was the electronics and information technology revolution, which emerged in the twentieth century and focused on automating production. The fourth is the artificial intelligence revolution, which came about thanks to the development of the computer industry and the emergence of the internet, smartphones, and robotics. This revolution has transformed the manufacturing sector in recent years. The Intelligent Manufacturing System (IMS) is a modern manufacturing system that integrates the capabilities of humans, machines, and processes to achieve the best possible manufacturing results through optimal use of manufacturing resources, reduced costs, and increased production flexibility. (Al-Beltagy, 2023, 307) The following is a presentation of some concepts from the perspectives of writers and researchers, as shown in the table. (1)

Table (1) Smart manufacturing concepts from the point of view of writers and researchers

N	The researcher & the Sunnah	The concept
1	(Fang, et.al,2017,2)	A combination of advanced manufacturing capabilities and digital technologies that work together to create highly reliable products with optimal costs, lead times, quality, safety, and environmental impact. The concept of smart manufacturing is closely linked to knowledge-based decision-making to meet customer product requirements and technical challenges such as security, disruption, and worker skill variability.
2	(Yang, et.al,2021,1225)	A vision for an optimal intelligent decision-making system based on human-machine collaboration and an autonomous intelligent control system, with the goal of achieving optimal control over comprehensive production indicators.
3	(Jan, rt.al,2021,507)	A technology-based approach that uses internet-connected machines and new hardware methods to monitor production processes,

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		increase flexibility, and support workers in their daily routines using innovative human-computer interaction methods.
4	(Cali,2022,2)	The ability to contribute to companies, with a great deal of digital technology, to increase the interconnectedness and cooperation of resources, both within them and along the supply chain, which achieves good results in the field with efficiency and effectiveness.
5	(Flores-Cerrillo et al,2023,2)	Smart manufacturing is simply the use of technologies and processes that leverage data and connectivity to improve safety, reliability, and efficiency in manufacturing industries.

Source: The table was prepared by the researchers based on the sources mentioned in the table.

Researchers define smart manufacturing procedurally as a modern concept that refers to the use of advanced technologies in manufacturing processes to improve efficiency, quality, and flexibility. This model relies on the integration of information technology, the Internet of Things, and artificial intelligence with manufacturing processes. It also aims to create a smart manufacturing environment that dynamically responds to changing market conditions and customer requirements.

Second: Smart Manufacturing Objectives

One of the most important objectives of smart manufacturing is its connection to technological developments, the dynamic requirements of stakeholders, and innovative business models. Smart manufacturing systems obtain real-time data, which improves decision-making accuracy, enhances plant efficiency, and increases productivity (Qu et al., 2019, 6).

Among the most important basic objectives of the smart manufacturing process (Tufan, Al-Awadi, 2023, 282) are:

1. **Autonomous Agile Processes:** The primary goal of establishing a smart manufacturing system is to achieve operational agility, increase efficiency, and autonomy of the manufacturing system. It is essential to develop an evaluation system that takes into account the changes in processes resulting from this autonomy. Smart manufacturing systems help users evaluate autonomous processes versus traditional processes.

2. **Sustainability and Value Addition:** Achieving sustainability in manufacturing requires a holistic approach that encompasses product design, the manufacturing process, manufacturing systems, and the entire supply chain. This goal is one of the objectives focused on in the lifecycle of smart manufacturing systems. He also pointed out that sustainability is one of the primary goals of smart manufacturing, and its importance stems from the growing concern for the environment and the depletion of natural resources. One of the most important concepts in smart manufacturing is improving energy efficiency, which means saving energy and reducing the consumption of natural resources. Therefore, energy efficiency is a sustainability solution.

3. **Partnerships: In autonomous work environments,** smart manufacturing systems aim to foster real-time and

continuous collaboration and achieve successful partnerships based on autonomous agile processes, sustainable value addition, and knowledge and information sharing to achieve shared development for multiple stakeholders and the emergence of a smart manufacturing system.

Third: Characteristics of Smart Manufacturing

One of the most important characteristics associated with smart manufacturing is its ability to be reconfigurable, flexible, low-cost, and adaptable or transformable. A smart factory requires a comprehensive system of planning and control tools that help integrate planning, simulation, and operations that support the entire product lifecycle (Machado et al., 2018, 333).

Therefore, researchers have identified several characteristics, technologies, and enabling factors associated with smart manufacturing. In an attempt to define these systems, we will address some of the characteristics as follows (Mittal et al., 2017, 5).

1- **Digitization:** Smart manufacturing systems possess a unique identity; they must have a digital presence, operating in a digital environment. That is, they must have a network interface address.

2- **Activity Description:** The activities carried out in the smart manufacturing system must be described, and the smart manufacturing system must be self-aware, i.e., aware of its current state.

3- **Composability:** The ability to understand the system based on the definition of its parts and the combination of its components.

4- **Interoperability:** The ability of systems to exchange and share information with each other, using networks and distributed systems.

5- **Decentralization:** This is a characteristic of smart manufacturing operating in a centralized manner.

6- **Integration:** These are characteristics resulting from the ability to integrate different units, which is linked to interoperability.

Among the most important features of smart manufacturing are increased flexibility, automation, intelligence, integration, and sustainability (Meng.et.al, 2018, 2).

Fourth: Dimensions of Smart Manufacturing

Smart manufacturing has an identity that can be demonstrated through the five dimensions below. However, these dimensions are neither final nor static. These dimensions will ultimately be determined by research and applications that may emerge in the future. Smart manufacturing relies on the following dimensions (Kusiak, 2017, 4-5; Wang & Hus, 2020, 12; Hawas & Werdi, 2021, 402; Taha & Hamid, 2025, 7):

1. **Manufacturing and information technologies:** As manufacturing technologies and processes are expected to emerge in various forms in the near future, the goal of smart manufacturing is to create production processes and manufacturing systems that are adaptable locally or globally by integrating advanced information technology, computing capabilities, and artificial intelligence, from a data-driven intelligence perspective. Instant messaging is used to obtain real-time data. And its distribution, analysis, and real-time use by humans, machines, and processes on shop floors, factories, and across product lifecycles.

2. **Materials:** Smart materials and products will take their own evolutionary path. Smart manufacturing is open to all types of materials, whether organic or organic, that will be used in future products. Each manufacturing company's use of materials varies, given the vast variety of products available on the market and the myriad of potential tools and combinations of materials and processes that can be used to move a product from raw material to finished product.

3. **Data:** We are witnessing a data revolution in manufacturing, some of which is the result of the development of sensors and wireless technologies and advances in data analytics. Smart manufacturing systems obtain real-time data that improves decision-making accuracy, enhances factory efficiency and performance, and increases overall productivity.

4. **Predictive Engineering:** Predictive engineering is one of the latest additions to manufacturing solutions that will lead to proactive, rather than reactive, organizations. The manufacturing industry has traditionally focused on the use of data for analysis, monitoring, and control, such as productivity analysis, process monitoring, and quality control.

5. **Sustainability:** Sustainability is critical in manufacturing, and sustainability efforts address manufacturing processes, energy use, and associated pollutants. The greatest sustainability gains are achieved when product and process development meets sustainability standards. Possible scenarios include:

- A. Sustainable product design drives manufacturing processes.
- B. Sustainable manufacturing processes influence product design.
- C. The simultaneous development of sustainable materials, products, and processes occurs simultaneously.

PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY

First: The Concept of Production Efficiency

Despite the importance of the topic of production efficiency, establishing a framework for its concept remains difficult, given the multiplicity of concepts and definitions, which encompass more than one meaning that varies depending on the intended meaning of the concept. The latter has a distinct meaning, arising from the close relationships between the productive elements when they are brought together in a single factory, requiring them to continually work to produce high-quality products. This means that production efficiency depends for its existence on fundamental components that emerge from within the factory itself.

Table (2): Concepts of Production Efficiency from the Perspectives of Writers and Researchers

N	The researcher & the Sunnah	The concept
1	(Sharouf, 2019, 29)	Production efficiency is a measure of the efficiency and ability of production factors to achieve the highest productivity. Examples include labor efficiency, site efficiency, efficiency of materials used, and efficiency of auxiliary materials.
2	(Musa, 2020, 331)	The optimal use of production elements and all available financial, human, material and information resources, with the aim of obtaining the maximum benefit from them, including scientific methods in management represented in planning, organization, guidance and control at a specific level, at a specific time and at the lowest cost.
3	(Greenwood, 2021, 12)	The dynamic engine of the production process, meaning that it is the source and energy that controls the performance of the various elements involved in the production process.
4	(Ezz El-Din, 2023, 199)	The ratio of the outputs of the production process to its inputs, and it divides it into the productivity of the worker, the machine, capital, and energy, in addition to the extent of achieving maximum benefit from the organization’s capabilities with the aim of reaching the best possible production.

5	(Ali.w,2024,3)	It is the relationship between the inputs of the production process on the one hand and the outputs resulting from this process on the other hand, where production efficiency increases as the percentage of output used from resources increases. It is the optimal use of production elements with the aim of achieving the greatest amount of production at a specific level at the lowest possible cost.
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Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the sources listed in the table.

Researchers believe that productive efficiency refers to a level of maximum capacity where all resources are fully utilized to produce the most cost-effective product possible, with the goal of achieving the best possible results.

Second: The Importance of Measuring Productive Efficiency

The topic of productive efficiency is of great interest to economic researchers, as it reflects an indicator of profitability, on the one hand, and the efficiency of performance in business establishments, on the other. What increases the importance of productive efficiency is the close relationship between productivity and the standard of living of both the individual and society. High productivity has positive effects on the establishment and its members as a whole. The importance of measuring productive efficiency is evident in that it reflects the extent of the success or failure of employees. There are some measures for measuring productivity, including the following: (Mufleh et al., 2018, 240)

1- Actual output: Focusing on numbers alone may create the impression that progress has been achieved. 2- Workload: The number of working hours spent completing a specific task is monitored. The fewer the working hours, the more efficient the performance. However, there is no evidence to confirm the effectiveness of the implemented program.

3- Service Level: Certain standards are derived in certain professional fields to determine the desired level and the progress achieved.

Among the reasons for the importance of measuring productivity efficiency, and making it a major focus for researchers across various disciplines, is its significant importance, evident in the following aspects (Ezz El-Din and Zaabat, 2023, 245):

1- As a fundamental pillar for improving productivity rates at the national level.

2- It is considered an important element for the success and sustainability of an institution.

3- As a general measure used to evaluate institutional performance, it reflects the extent of management's success

or failure in investing or operating capital and achieving targeted results.

4- Productivity is an important indicator that indicates the degree of development and progress enjoyed by the national economy of any given country. Therefore, productivity has an impact on the economic development of a given country.

Third: Methods for Improving Production Efficiency

Through our study of the factors affecting production efficiency previously explained, two basic approaches can be identified for improving production efficiency:

1. **The Technical Approach:** Production efficiency can be improved by adopting the technical approach through developing product manufacturing processes. This involves studying and developing product design, factory design, controlling material flow, and quality control. This includes adopting production policies aimed at increasing production efficiency. Among the technical approach production policies that can be adopted are: (Ibrahim and Mustafa, 2020, 17)

- A. The mass production policy.
- B. The specialization policy.
- C. The simplification policy.
- D. The standardization policy.

2- **The human approach:** Production efficiency can be improved by following the methods that aim to develop the relationship between management and the working forces through developing the morale of workers, taking care to organize supervision, paying attention to training workers and raising their efficiency, appointing the right person in the appropriate job position, paying attention to promotion and good treatment of workers, and providing them with social, health and entertainment services to motivate them to perform and increase productivity (Khamis, 2018, 271).

Section Three: Concerning the Field (Practical) Aspect

First: Testing Hypotheses at the Sinjar Cement Plant:

1. **Measuring Correlation Relationships:** Table (3) displays the nature of the correlation relationships between the research variables at the Northern General Cement Company (Sinjar Cement Plant).

Table (3): Correlation Relationships at the Sinjar Cement Plan

Dimensions of Smart Manufacturing	Manufacturing techniques	Materials	Data	Predictive engineering	Sustainability	Total index
Production Efficiency	0.799*	0.898*	0.844	0.599*	0,303 ^{n.s}	0.909*

p ≤ 0.05 N = 34

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Table (3), which deals with the nature of the correlation between the research variables at Sinjar Cement Factory, shows that there is a strong, statistically significant correlation. A significant, positive correlation was proven between smart manufacturing and production efficiency, with the correlation coefficient value reaching (0.909) at a significance level of (0.05), indicating a strong correlation. At the micro level, a correlation was also proven between each

dimension, except for the sustainability dimension, and production efficiency, with the correlation coefficient values being (0.799, 0.898, 0.833, 0.599, 0.303 n.s), respectively.

2. Measuring Influential Relationships: Table (4) shows the nature of the influencing relationships between the research variables at the Northern Cement General Company (Sinjar Cement Factory):

Table (4) Influential Relationships at the Macro Level

Independent Variable	Smart manufacturing		R ²	F	
Dependent Variable	B0	B1		The calculated	Tabular
Production Efficiency	0.252	1.039 (12.373)	0.827	153	2.00

P ≤ 0.05 N= 34 d.f(1,32)

Table (4) shows the existence of a strong significant influence relationship between the independent variable (smart manufacturing) and the dependent variable (production efficiency), as the calculated value of (F) reached (153), which is higher than the table value at two degrees of freedom (1, 32). By following the beta coefficient of the T-test, we

find that a change in the influential variable by one unit leads to an estimation in the affected variable by (1.039), and that this influence is real, as evidenced by the calculated T value of (12.273), which is greater than its table value of (1.978) at a significance level of (0.05) and a sample size of (n=34).

Table (5) Influence relationships at the micro-level

Independent Variable	Dimensions of smart manufacturing						R ²		
Dependent Variable	B0	B1	B2	B3	B4	B5		The calculated	Tabular
Production Efficiency	0.019	0.264 (4.365)	0.242 (4.037)	0.329 (5.414)	0.242 (4.040)	0.094 (2.088)	0.945	96.219	2.00

P ≤ 0.05 N= 34 d.f(1,28)

Table (5), which measures the impact relationships at the micro-level, shows the impact of each dimension of smart manufacturing as an influencing variable on production efficiency as an affected variable. We note a significant impact for each dimension of smart manufacturing on production efficiency, with the highest impact being for the data dimension, which reached an impact value of (0.329), meaning that a change in this dimension by one unit leads to a change in the dependent variable by this amount. This is a real impact, as evidenced by the calculated (T) value, which reached (5.414), which is greater than its tabular value of (1.98) at a significance level of (0.05) and a sample size of (n=34). The sustainability dimension had the lowest impact,

with an impact value of (0.094), while the impact of both the materials and predictive engineering dimensions was equal, with an impact value of (0.242).

Second: Testing the research hypotheses at Badoush Cement Plant:

1. **Measuring correlations:** Table (6) shows the nature of the correlations between the research variables at the Northern Cement General Company (Badoush Cement Plant).

Table (6) Correlational relationships at Badoush Cement Plant

Dimensions of Smart Manufacturing	Manufacturing techniques	Materials	Data	Predictive engineering	Sustainability	Total index
Production Efficiency	0.661*	0.582*	0.552*	0.589*	0.834*	0.840*

p ≤ 0.05 N= 34

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Table (6) on the nature of the correlations between the research variables at Badoush Cement Plant shows that there is a strong, statistically significant correlation. A significant, positive correlation was proven between smart manufacturing and production efficiency, with the correlation coefficient value reaching (0.840) at a significance level of (0.05), indicating a strong correlation. At the micro level, a correlation was also proven between each dimension, except

for the sustainability dimension, and production efficiency, with the correlation coefficient values being (0.661, 0.582, 0.552, 0.589, 0.834), respectively.

2. Measuring Influential Relationships: Table (7) shows the nature of the influencing relationships between the research variables at the Northern Cement General Company (Badoush Cement Plant):

Table (7) Impact relationship at the aggregate level

Independent Variable	Smart manufacturing		R ²	F	
Dependent Variable	B0	B1		The calculated	Tabular
Production Efficiency	0.172	1.035 (8.742)	0.705	76.415	2.00

P ≤ 0.05 N= 34 d.f(1,32)

Table (7) shows the existence of a strong significant influence relationship between the influencing variable (smart manufacturing) and the affected variable (production efficiency), as the calculated value of (F) reached (76.415), which is higher than the table value at two degrees of freedom

(1, 32). By following the beta coefficient of the T-test, we find that a change in the influencing variable by one unit leads to an estimation in the affected variable by (1.035), and that this effect is real, as evidenced by the fact that the calculated T value of (8.742) is greater than its table value of (1.978) at a significance level of (0.05) and a sample size of (n=34).

Table (8) Influence relationships at the micro-level

Independent Variable	Dimensions of smart manufacturing						R ²		
	B0	B1	B2	B3	B4	B5		The calculated	Tabular
Production Efficiency	0.130	0.160 (1.218)	0.144 (1.393)	0.001 (0.004)	0.177 (1.354)	0.483 (5.798)	0.800	22.397	2.00

P ≤ 0.05 N= 34 d.f(1,28)

Table (8), which measures the impact relationships at the micro-level, shows the impact of each dimension of smart manufacturing as an independent variable on production efficiency as a dependent variable. We note a significant impact for each dimension of smart manufacturing on production efficiency. The highest impact was for the sustainability dimension, which reached an impact value of (0.483), meaning that a change in this dimension by one unit leads to a change in the dependent variable by this amount. This is a real impact, as evidenced by the calculated (T) value

of (5.798), which is greater than its table value of (1.98) at a significance level of (0.05) and a sample size of (n=28). The least impact was for the data dimension, with an impact value of (0.001)

Third: Testing the research hypotheses at the Hammam Al-Alil Cement Plant:

1. Measuring correlations: Table (9) shows the nature of the correlations between the research variables at the Northern General Cement Company (Hammam Al-Alil Cement Plant):

Table (9): Correlational relationships at the Hammam Al-Alil Cement Plant

Dimensions of Smart Manufacturing	Manufacturing techniques	Materials	Data	Predictive engineering	Sustainability	Total index
Production Efficiency	0.043 ^{N.S}	0.383*	0.486*	0.553*	0.011 ^{N.S}	0.547*

p ≤ 0.05 N= 34

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Table (9), which deals with the nature of the correlations between the research variables at the Hammam Al-Alil Cement Plant, shows that there is a strong, statistically significant correlation. A significant positive correlation was proven between smart manufacturing and production efficiency, with the overall correlation coefficient value reaching (0.547) at a significance level of (0.05), indicating a strong correlation. At the micro level, a significant correlation was also proven between each dimension (materials, data,

and engineering) and production efficiency, with the correlation coefficient values being (0.383, 0.486, and 0.553), respectively. The relationship between the manufacturing technologies and sustainability dimensions was not strong.

2. **Measuring Influential Relationships:** Table (10) shows the nature of the influencing relationships between the research variables at the Northern Cement General Company (Badush Cement Plant):

Table (10) Impact relationship at the aggregate level

Independent Variable	Smart manufacturing		R ²	F	
Dependent Variable	B0	B1		The calculated	Tabular
Production Efficiency	1.940	1.359 (3.694)	0.299	13.647	2.00

P ≤ 0.05 N= 34 d.f(1,32)

Table (10) shows a strong significant influence relationship between the influencing variable (smart manufacturing) and the influenced variable (production efficiency), as the calculated (F) value reached (13.647), which is higher than the table value at two degrees of freedom (1, 32). By following the beta coefficient of the T-test, we find that a

change in the influencing variable by one unit leads to a change in the influenced variable by (1.359), and that this effect is real, as evidenced by the calculated T value of (3.694), which is greater than its table value of (1.678) at a significance level of (0.05) and a sample size of (n=34).

Table (11) Influence relationships at the micro-level

Independent Variable	Dimensions of smart manufacturing						R ²		
Dependent Variable	B0	B1	B2	B3	B4	B5		The calculated	Tabular
Production Efficiency	1.538	0.034 (0.198)	0.106 (0.543)	0.677 (3.301)	0.556 (3.280)	0.113 (0.692)	0.525	6.183	2.00

P ≤ 0.05 N= 34 d.f(1,28)

Table (11) for measuring the impact relationships at the micro level shows the impact of each dimension of smart manufacturing as independent variables on production efficiency as a dependent variable, where the highest impact was for the data dimension, which reached an impact value of (0.677), meaning that a change in this dimension by one unit leads to a change in the dependent variable by this amount, and this is a real impact, as evidenced by the calculated (T) value, which reached (3.301), which is greater than its tabular value of (1.678) at a significance level of (0.05) and a sample size of (n=28). The manufacturing technologies dimension had the lowest impact, with an impact value of (0.034).

Section Four: Conclusions and Recommendations

First: Conclusions: Based on the theoretical analysis of the research variables and the practical analysis of the research

variables in the field under study, we can draw the following important conclusions:

1. Competition, capturing market share, and meeting the needs and desires of rapidly changing customers cannot be achieved without transitioning to a smart manufacturing system in light of rapid technological progress.
2. The proper use of resources, especially natural resources, must be achieved using the best means and technologies to ensure optimal utilization of resources for the current generation and a sustainable share for future generations through the use of smart technologies.
3. It has been proven that there are correlations and the impact of smart manufacturing and production efficiency at the macro level and between each dimension of smart manufacturing and production efficiency, i.e., at the micro level, in the Sinjar Cement Plant, indicating the readiness of

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the field under study to absorb and apply the research variables.

4. It has been proven that there are strong correlations between smart manufacturing and production efficiency, both collectively and individually, in the Badush Cement Plant. Regarding the impact relationships, the relationship between smart manufacturing and production efficiency at the overall level was strongly significant. However, at the level of smart manufacturing dimensions, the impact relationship was not significant, except for the sustainability dimension.

5. The correlation between smart manufacturing and production efficiency was positive. However, the impact relationships at the level of the independent variable smart manufacturing dimensions and the dependent variable production efficiency were not positive. Regarding the impact relationships, it was also proven that smart manufacturing had an impact on overall production efficiency. However, at the level of smart manufacturing dimensions, the impact was only for the data and predictive engineering dimension at the Hammam Al-Alil Cement Plant.

Second: Proposals: Based on the results achieved and the conclusions drawn, some important proposals can be included:

1. The Northern Cement General Company should introduce smart manufacturing technologies and work to understand and apply this important manufacturing system in production processes, as it brings numerous benefits at the individual, organizational, societal, and national levels.

2. The need to establish partnerships with educational and research institutions, such as universities and research centers, to organize practical training courses and form teams to properly implement smart manufacturing and achieve the desired results from this system.

3. The need to explore any means that lead to increasing and improving production efficiency and the proper use of resources, especially natural resources, as these are the most important means for developing countries and revitalizing the economy, thus achieving prosperity for the current and future generations through sustainable development.

4. One of the best ways to increase and improve production efficiency is to invest in science by acquiring and applying modern technologies in the field of industry, optimally utilizing resources, reducing waste, and preserving the environment and natural resources without exposing them to the risk of depletion and waste in use.

5. Smart manufacturing has brought about many major changes in various fields, as it has achieved a qualitative shift in the manufacturing of various products and services through a group of advanced technologies, the most important of which are (artificial intelligence, e-learning, the Internet of Things, cloud computing, and virtual reality), as the use of

these technologies has led to achieving amazing results in completing work with ease, speed, and very high efficiency.

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